

EFFECT OF CHEMICAL MODIFICATION FOR KENAF FIBER ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FURAN BASED NFRP

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ABSTRACT

NFRPs have recently attracted attention due to its derivation from renewable plant resources. Natural fiber reinforced plastics (NFRPs) are recognized as an alternative for synthetic composites, *ex. GFRPs*. Although GFRP laminates shows excellent mechanical properties, and many advantages, the dwindling of the fossil resources has increased an interest in developing renewable materials. From these background, it is necessary to invest a sustainability and to provide a feasible disposability in matrix of NFRPs as PLA or other biodegradable polymers. Furan resin made from corn cob or other vegetable resources is one of the green plastics which will lead to the reduction of environmental load and petroleum consumption. This resin is thermoset which has a higher resistance to chemical and heat than the other plant-derived thermoplastics. Then, NFRPs with long-life durability and high mechanical performance can be aimed by this resin. However because of this resin is very brittle and curing mechanism has not been cleared, when being used as a composite matrix material it is difficult to molding even into a sheet shape. In previous research, this weakness was improved by adding hydrogen peroxide and applying high pressure using a hot press, but the desirable performance was not accomplished. In this study, through curing reaction and interfacial chemical bonding analysis, an approach to increase the strength and toughness of furan resin was tried. From revision of curing temperature and curing time, average flexural strength was improved to 280 MPa, and average elastic modulus was improved to 25 GPa. Furthermore, adding salicylaldehyde to the interface of NFRP allowed 310 MPa of flexural strength and 27.5 MPa of elastic modulus.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fiber reinforced plastics (NFRPs) are recognized as an alternative for GFRPs. The dwindling of the fossil resources has increased the interest in developing renewable polymers [1]. Using furan resin which made from corn cob or other vegetable resources, will lead to reduction of environmental load and petroleum consumption. This resin is thermoset which has higher resistance to chemical and heat than the other plant-derived thermoplastics [2].

However, one of the most general disadvantages of NFRPs is their small strength compared to the mechanical performance of GFRP composites due to the interfacial weakness. In previous research, this weakness was improved by applying high pressure using hot press, but the desirable performance was not accomplished [3].

The purpose of this paper is to discuss how to improve interfacial bonding and to raise mechanical strength of furan resin through curing reaction analysis.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

Furan resin (supplied by Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd.) was prepared with *p*-alkylbenzene sulfonic acid solution as a curing agent. Hydrogen peroxide solution was prepared as curing accelerator [3]. Salicylaldehyde was also prepared for improvement of interfacial bonding. Dried kenaf bast fiber was prepared as natural fiber reinforcement. Sodium hydroxide was prepared for alkali treatment solution to extract lignin from natural fibers.

2.2 CURING METHOD OF NEAT FURAN RESIN

Generally, furan resin is cured by acidic curing agent with reaction promoter by oxygen [4]. In the previous study [3], furan resin including curing agent with hydrogen peroxide solution has more mechanical strength than without hydrogen peroxide solution. If more than 4 phr of hydrogen peroxide solution is added, a runaway reaction shall be occurred. In the previous study, 2.5 phr was considered as the best portion.

Furan resin and p-alkylbenzene sulfonic acid solution (curing agent) and hydrogen peroxide solution were mixed in a ratio of 100:0.85:2.50 (120g, 1.02g, 3.00g) respectively, and then a cup of mixture was degassed by vacuum deaerator to remove dissolved gas. When making a neat cured resin, the mixture poured into a square plate shaped mold was pressed at 1.4 MPa by using hot press to avoid warpage. The curing process is divided into 4 steps to avoid rapid reaction: furan resin in mold was heated at 30°C for 2 h; 65°C for 3 h; 115°C for 4 h; 145°C for 4 h. For comparison, pressure was released once or twice around 100°C to let out steam.

2.3 FIBER TREATMENT

Generally, cellulose in natural fibre is covered with lignin. Although cellulose has high tensile strength (2 to 6 GPa, higher than steel), lignin makes natural fibre brittle and low mechanical properties. Therefore, it is expected that natural fibre is improved by removing lignin from fiber. In this study, immersion in alkali aqueous solution to remove lignin was adopted.

2.4 INSTALLATION OF SALICYLALDEHYDE

Generally, furan resin is polymerized by attacking alpha position of a furfuryl alcohol. Furthermore in previous study [3], it was proposed that a part of furan resin polymerization or cross-linking was promoted by attacking beta position. This reaction begins an electrophilic attack against carbon at beta position of furan ring. From this fact it is anticipated another reagent which can react to furan resin to connect resin and fiber. Selecting method of the interfacial adhesion agent is as follows: it should be a liquid (easy to apply to kenaf fiber), an aromatic compound (to supply an electrophilicity), hydrophilic compound (to become attached with natural fiber) and high boiling point (to avoid vaporizing between manufacturing NFRP). From these selecting points, salicylaldehyde was selected as the interfacial adhesion agent.

Fig.1: Polymerized reaction by attacking alpha position of furan ring

Fig.2: Polymerized reaction by attacking beta position of furan ring

Fig.3: Anticipated reaction of furan resin and salicylaldehyde

Fig.4: Anticipated reaction of kenaf fiber and salicylaldehyde

2.5 MANUFACTURING METHOD OF FURAN BASED NFRP

At the beginning, dried kenaf fiber was cut into 20cm length and 12g weight to be divided to 5 bunches. Then treated with 5 mass % NaOH solution at 80°C for several hours. Afterwards, the treated fibers are cooled down to room temperature and neutralized with 0.01 mol/L hydrochloric acid for an hour. Acid side is preferable to curing of furan resin. Fibers are then pressed into five fiber sheets, and, were dried to remove excess moisture. Furan resin and *p*-alkylbenzene sulfonic acid solution (curing agent) and hydrogen peroxide solution were mixed in a ratio of 100:0.85:2.50 (80g, 0.68g, 2.00g), respectively. Apart from this resin component, mixture of 40g furan resin and 0.34g of curing agent was prepared, because kenaf fiber is damaged by hydrogen peroxide solution, so it is necessary to separate a hydrogen peroxide solution from fiber [3]. Salicylaldehyde was dropped to all fiber sheets and then furan resin without hydrogen peroxide solution was applied on the sheets directly by hand. After that, hydrogen peroxide solution-added furan resin was impregnated. The curing process is divided into 4 steps as mentioned in chapter 2.2.

3 EVALUATION METHOD

3.1 DSC test

To evaluate degree of cure, DSC (DSC-9100, ULVAC RIKO *Inc.*) was used to detect existence of exothermic peak of furan resin. For this test, alpha alumina was used as reference material.

3.2 Tensile test for kenaf fiber

To evaluate tensile property of kenaf fiber, kenaf fiber was separated to a fiber, subject to appropriate JIS methods for measuring tensile strength of natural fiber (JIS L1069:2002). Tests were done by using a universal testing machine; (Shimadzu Autograph, AGS-J-1kN). When decided the optimum alkali treatment time, 80°C, 5 mass % of sodium hydroxide between 2 to 11 hours were used as a treatment conditions.

3.3 Bending test

To evaluate mechanical property of cured neat furan resin and manufactured NFRP, the sample was cut into the test sample sizes subject to appropriate JIS methods for measuring flexural properties. The three-point bending tests (JIS K7017:1999) were done using a universal testing machine (Shimadzu Autograph, AGS-J-1kN).

3.4 FT-IR test

To detect the influence of salicylaldehyde on chemical structure of NFRP, FT-IR analysis (FTIR-8300, Shimadzu Corporation) was conducted. Upon this analysis, the test sample was cut carefully from cross-section of the 5 layered plate and measured by a KBr pellet method.

3.5 SEM observation

To observe changes in the condition of kenaf fiber by alkali treatment, scanning electron microscope (JSM-5310LV, JEOL *Ltd.*) was used.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Mechanical property of furan resin for curing time

Fig.5 is the results of the cyclic DSC test for cured furan resin from room temperature to 180°C quarterly. In a previous study, it was detected that furan resin has large exothermic peak at 110 and 140 degrees. According to this test, exothermic peak was still observed (1st scan). As the test was repeated, exothermic peak became smaller. So it could be assumed that completely cured furan resin is achieved by highly heating condition. As illustrated in Table 1, various patterns were set as heating condition by oven (pattern A is conventional method mentioned in chapter 2.2).

In the DSC test results of resin by new curing methods, as illustrated in Fig. 6, exothermic peak was decreased by extending curing time and temperature. From these results pattern E illustrated in table 1 was chosen for manufacturing method of this furan based NFRP.

Fig. 5: Cyclic DSC test for cured furan resin

Table 1: Patterns of reheating time

	A	B	C	D	E
115°C×4h	-	○	○	-	○
145°C×4h	-	-	○	-	○
145°C×8h	-	-	-	○	○

Fig.6: DSC curves of reheated furan resin

4.2 Effects of alkali treatment time to kenaf fiber

Fig.7 shows the tensile strength of alkali treated kenaf fiber. Although there is large scattering, the tensile strength is improved little by little at extending treatment time. However, after 10 hours the value is declined expected as too long treatment time to remove lignin and to control form damage on cellulose, conversely. When manufacturing NFRP, 9 hours alkali treatment was selected which had an ultimate level of tensile strength.

From SEM observation, non-treatment fiber is covered with lignin or other impurities shown in Fig. 8. A fiber treated 9 hours shows that adhered substances is removed, but treated 11 hours seems to be damaged.

Fig.7 Influence of alkali treatment time for tensile strength of kenaf fiber

Fig.8: Kenaf fiber after alkali treatment (a: 0 hours, b: 9 hours, c: 11 hours)

4.3 Mechanical property of NFRP for curing time

From the result of DSC test (chapter 4.1), heating time was newly determined in this study. Comparison between the previous method and the reheated NFRP sample programmed as “E” are shown in Fig. 9.

Fig.9: Elastic modulus and flexural strength of NFRP at different curing time

From this consequence, extending the curing time and temperature allowed significant flexural strength and flexural modulus of NFRP. The flexural strength shows 280 MPa which is remarkable increase from previous result. As the result of these mechanical properties, by completely cured furan resin, it was allowed to receive more stress to furan resin.

4.4 Effects of salicylaldehyde to interfacial adhesion of NFRP

To bond resin and fiber well, various amounts of salicylaldehyde (0 ml, 3 ml, 10 ml, 15 ml, and 20 ml per 1 sample) were applied on the kenaf sheet used for interface treatment agent. Flexural strength and elastic modulus were measured for each sample. As a result, mechanical strength is improved as the amount of salicylaldehyde is increased, but excessively added over 15 ml per 5 sets of kenaf sheet makes mechanical strength lower, conversely. Excess salicylaldehyde which could not react with furan resin and kenaf fiber which applied into the composite may disturb polymerization reaction of furan resin. So, it was decided to add 10 ml of salicylaldehyde as the NFRP manufacturing condition.

Fig.10: Effects of salicylaldehyde to NFRP cured by conventional method

Fig.11: Effects of salicylaldehyde to mechanical strength of NFRP insofar as reheated

From these results, it can be considered that the mechanical strength of NFRP is improved by salicylaldehyde as an interfacial modifier. This results shows that interfacial modifier increases flexural strength over 310 MPa and flexural modulus over 27.5 GPa which successfully enhanced from full-cured one shown in Fig. 9. For confirming chemical bonding with furan resin and kenaf fiber, FT-IR analysis was conducted.

Fig.12: FT-IR spectra of NFRP which included salicylaldehyde or not

From Fig.12, it turns out that alpha-branching secondary alcohol (1050 cm^{-1}) and aromatic ether (1275 cm^{-1}) peak is detected from salicylaldehyde included NFRP in comparison with the control sample. So it is considered there is a chemical bond between furan resin and kenaf fiber through the salicylaldehyde.

Fig.13: Chemical structure of NFRP bonded by salicylaldehyde

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this research, to make high performance furan resin based natural fiber reinforced composite material, an effort to clarify curing mechanism and to improve interfacial adhesion strength were conducted. From the results, enough curing time and high temperature allowed complete curing and achieving more elastic modulus. Average flexural strength was achieved 280 MPa and average elastic modulus was achieved 25 GPa, and these values were more than twice as compared with conventionally-processed NFRP. Furthermore, adding salicylaldehyde to the interface of NFRP allowed 310 MPa of flexural strength and 27.5 MPa of elastic modulus. These values correspond to a flexural strength of general GFRPs. In the future, it is anticipated to displace GFRP to NFRP which made with all sustainable resources, and at that time proposed manufacturing process will be key method.

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